

A Person-group Fit Model as an Antecedent of Group Performance

Işık Çiçek^{a *}, İsmail Hakkı Biçer^b

^a*Okan University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Istanbul, 34959, Turkey*

^b*Istanbul Technical University, Faculty of Management, Istanbul, 34367, Turkey*

Abstract

Depending on the effect of technology on organizations and work, a remarkable factor for solving human-oriented problems is having an employee congruent with his/her group. Considering fit as a tool for creating this employee profile has become a research topic in the field of human resource management for the last several years. One of the effects related to fit/misfit is group performance. The effect of employees' fit with their group on the performance of working group is investigated in this research. Person-group fit is investigated by means of 3 dimensions: the employees' perception about demographic similarity with group members (relational demography, similarity of personal values with group values, and congruence of personality traits with group members' ones). 124 working group-sampling is selected at technology based organizations. The volume of selected sampling is 640 employees. Proposed relationships are tested by means of structural equation modelling at lisrel program. According to findings, employees' perception of demographic similarity concerning group and value fit affect group performance, positively as expected. Contrary to expectations, personality traits similarity with group members explain the variance in the group performance, negatively.

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Keywords: Values, personality traits, relational demography, group performance, human resource management

1. Introduction

Intellectual capital gain importance in today's environment. Awareness of demographic, dispositional and socio-cultural differentiations that employees face is a critical phenomenon for managers so as to utilize differentiations and minimize their adverse effects (George and Chattopadhyay, 2002; Erdoğan et. al, 2004). Depending on technological development, the nature of jobs in technology-based organizations highlights group working. Therefore, the antecedents of fit between group and intellectual capital that is a critical input for groups are paid attention. Project-type works operated in technology-based organizations increase the necessity of group working. Group performance can be related to person-group fit. The aim of this research is to investigate the antecedents of person-group fit on the group performance.

2. Theoretical framework and hypotheses

2.1. Antecedents of person-group fit

Organizational working groups (i.e. geographical sub-units) have unique norms and values different from organizations in which there are (Schein, 1992; Werbel and Johnson, 2001). Therefore, fit between person and sub-units will be different from person-organization fit (Kristof, 1996). The effects of local culture and frequent communication among the employees working in the same location mean for person-group fit more than person-organization fit (Metzler, 2005).

Person-group fit depends on the notion that position in the work requires interaction among employees. PG fit identifies both supplementary and complementary aspects of fit necessary for successfully working with co-workers in a workgroup or a team (Werbel & Gilliland, 1999). Supplementary fit involves employees sharing similar

* E-mail address: cicekis@yahoo.com

attributes among their group members, whereas complementary fit is concerned with providing the skills and abilities that are not widely shared by other group members (Muchinsky & Monahan, 1987; Werbel, DeMarie, 2005). Because all group members have essential features and some missing affecting group performance, the performance increase the time an employee's lack is complemented by other group members' remarkable properties. Therefore, complementary fit depends on determining human resource inadequacy in a working group and diagnosing necessary human resource features to develop (Edwards and Cooper, 1990; Werbel and Johnson, 2001).

Beside to describing person-group fit by supplementary and complementary perspectives, the dimensions of fit can be explained via some definitions in the literature. A definition is "the similarity degree of an employee personality with other members' personalities in the group. Ferris et al (1985) define person-group fit as similarity in the personality traits (Shin, 2005).

Organizations consists of sub-cultures affected by hierarchical levels and functional/departmental structure (Rousseau, 1990). These differences cause to consider a new approach by researchers to evaluate person-organization fit regardless of consistency among perceived organizational values. The necessity becomes more important due to increment in the number of sub-cultures depending on differentiations in the workplace (Warren, 1996; Verquer, 2002). The groups share common values. It can be expressed that value congruence is a dimension of person-group fit. The value dimension of person-group fit is congruence between personal values and values prevailing in the working group or shared by group members.

An employee's demographic similarity with group members can be considered as a dimension of person-group fit. Pfeffer (1983) stated that demographic similarity with group affects organization related outputs such as creativity, performance, managerial success. According to Pfeffer, to investigate synchronous demographic features such as age, gender and education level have more valuable instead of individual effects (O'Reilly et al, 1989; Surgevil, 2008). Therefore, the term relational demography is introduced. Relational demography posits regular interaction among employees due to their positions in groups. Comparing demographic similarity among group members can explain attitude and behaviors of employees. That is to say, the demographic characteristics affecting work outputs are appeared (Tsui and O'Reilly, 1989). Lots of demography researchers focused on variables of age and tenure for investigating effect on turnover. However, when analyzing the effects of demography, all characteristics should be considered together. Demographic profile for the group is made, afterwards (Tsui and O'Reilly, 1989; Surgevil, 2008). Perceptual similarity is a fit type that can be investigated in relational demography. Self categorization process describe group attractiveness in the light of psychological group emerged via perceptual similarity/differentiation with group members. These features can be related vocational and functional categories, as well (Surgevil, 2008).The employees different from counterparts attribute psychological meanings to these differentiations (Turner et al, 1989; Riordan, 2000). Williams and O'Reilly (1989) highlighted adverse effects of differentiations on group process depending on the degree of feeling about similarity/dissimilarity with group members. Actual dissimilarity results in perceptual demographic dissimilarity, and then outputs emerge. Attraction among people due to similarity of attitudes and experiences (Byrne, 1971) strengthen communication among employees (Roberts and O'Reilly, 1979; Surgevil, 2008). When group members have common attitudes regarding job execution, it is strongly possible to collaborate. Otherwise, conflict occurs (Molleman and Slomp, 2006). Therefore, similarity of employees attitudes regarding job execution with those of coworkers/supervisors can be research in this study.

Three dimensions of person-group fit (value, personality traits and perceptual demographic/attitude similarity) cause desired positive outputs in accordance with similarity-attraction theory and social categorization theory. Similarity/attraction theory (Byrne, 1971) posits that people like and are attracted to others who are similar, rather than dissimilar, to themselves. Before explaining self categorization theory, it is useful to mentioned about the term social identity. A social identity is the portion of an individual's self-concept derived from perceived membership in a relevant social group (Tajfel and Turner 1979). Social identity theory is best described as a theory that predicts certain intergroup behaviours on the basis of perceived group status differences, the perceived legitimacy and stability of those status differences, and the perceived ability to move from one group to another. Self-categorization process describes the circumstances under which a person will perceive collections of people (including themselves)

as a group, as well as the consequences of perceiving people in group terms. Although the theory is often introduced as an explanation of psychological group formation, it is more accurately thought of as general analysis of the functioning of categorization processes in social perception and interaction that speaks to issues of individual identity as much as group phenomena. Social categorization theory was in part developed to address questions that arose in response to social identity theory about the mechanistic underpinnings of social identification. People divided the world into “them” and “us” based through a process of social categorization. This is known as in-group (us) and out-group (them). Social identity theory states that the in-group will discriminate against the out-group to enhance their self-image. According to these propositions, the employee who is fit with group in terms of values, personality traits and perceptual demographic, attitudinal features will carry out social categorization with in-group.

2.2. Person-group fit and group performance

Several research shows that similarity among group members affect group decisions, positively (Klimoski and Jones, 1995, Yang et al, 2008). Supplementary fit (value fit, personality traits fit and relational demography) causing communication with other members to increase is related to group productivity and performance because it strengthens employee interactions. Socialization in group will be easier and the employee collaborates with others. Group synergy and performance will develop (Mullen and Cooper, 1994; Stanley, 2001). Because productivity in unit level is a function of employees’ collective productivity (Payne, 2000), it is influenced by norms and interactions among employees affect emerging of group performance (Whitman et. al, 2010). Perceived person-group fit in team level has a positive relationship with organizational citizenship behavior in team level. Increased collaboration among employees cause group performance to develop (Shin, 2005).

Hobman and Bordia (2006) revealed that value dissimilarity influenced duty conflict, positively. Zenger and Lawrence (1989) reported that similarity in terms of age and tenure for project group members was related to technical communication frequency (Simon et. al, 2010). Henttoren et. al (2010) found negative relationship between gender dissimilarity and team performance in their research. Pelled et. al (1999) found that demographic differentiations in groups influence conflict, in turn group performance. Considering the findings reported for 50 years, demographic dissimilarities such as gender and age affect efficiency of group functioning, negatively (Sürgevil, 2008).

In the light of theoretical knowledge explained and previous research findings, the hypotheses below can be proposed for this research:

H₁ : Similarity between personal values and values prevailing in group affects group performance, positively.

H₂ : Similarity between employee’s personality traits and other members’ personality traits in group affects group performance, positively

H₃: Employee’s perception about demographic similarity with group members and similarity between individual’s attitudes towards job execution and those of co-workers/supervisors affects group performance, positively.

3. Research

3.1. Sampling

Sampling is selected from technology-based organizations. Technology and information-systems units of banks, software companies, production firms including high-tech R&D department, communication and GSM operators are the types of firms in which the research is carried out. 640 employees (124 working groups) participate in this research.

3.2. Methodology and Scales

Supplementary fit is evaluated for the dimensions of value and personality traits. Values are determined for two times: personal values and values prevailing in group. Value congruence is measured via absolute difference between personal values and group values as other fit researches (i.e. Enz, 1998; Yıldırımbulut, 2006; Güneşer, 2007; Çiçek, 2013). Personality traits congruence is calculated via absolute difference between employee's trait and mean trait score of other group members excluded focal individual trait (Kristof-Brown et. al, 2005; Çiçek, 2013). The more the difference is, the less the supplementary fit is. Demographic similarity and job execution similarity is evaluated via employee perception.

Values: Short version (40 items) of Organizational Culture Profile originally developed by O'Reillt et. al (1991) is utilized for determining values. Cable and Judge (1996) tested reliability and validity of 40-item scale. Seven dimensions of values are innovation, stability, respect for people, outcome orientation, attention to detail, team orientation, and aggressiveness. Items are evaluated via 5-degree Likert scale.

Personality traits: 60-item NEO-PIR (NEO Five Factor Personality, Costa and McCrae, 1991) is utilized for determining five global personality factor: neuroticism, extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness. Reliability and validity of Turkish version are carried out by Gulgoz. Items are evaluated via 5-degree Likert scale.

Demographic similarity and job execution similarity: Demographic similarity perception for group members is evaluated in terms of age, gender, marital status, education level, organizational tenure. Total five items are asked, and each of them is designed for one demographic characteristic. Furthermore, perception of job execution similarity with group members and supervisor is evaluated by means of 2 items.

Group performance: Mixed scale is utilized for this research. 4 items are taken from Turkish version of performance scale developed by Beffort and Hatturp (2003). Karakurum (2005) translated the items in her study. Rewording "individual" as working group in items for this research. In this way, group performance is appraised via individual perception instead of individual performance measured in Beffort and Hatturp's study. 2 items are taken from team performance evaluation scale developed by Shin (2005). Total 6-item scale is made for evaluating performance group.

4. Findings

4.1. Reliability and validity of scales

Difference between personal values and group values: Before calculating differences, internal reliability is calculated for personal values and group values, separately. Cronbach alpha is 0.854 and 0.925 for these scales, respectively. Exploratory factor analysis is carried out for difference scores. Dimensions and internal reliability are shown at Table 1. (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin: 0.90; Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: 0.00)

Table 1 :Exploratory factor analysis for person values-group values

Factor	Items	Factor Loads	Eigenvalue	Explained variance (%)	Sub-scale reliability
1	12. people oriented	0.621	7.289	13.271	0.821
	13. fairness	0.657			
	14. tolerance	0.813			
	15. informality	0.641			
	17. supportive	0.611			
	20. being reflective	0.551			
	29. developing friends at work	0.481			
2	24. opportunities for professional growth	0.510	2.235	9.870	0.773
	25. high pay for good performance	0.796			
	26. security of employment	0.776			
	27. offers praise for good performance	0.747			
3	1. adaptability	0.770	1.657	8.570	0.192
	3. being innovative	0.598			
	6. autonomy (R)	-0.530			
	8. Being analytical	0.580			
4	28. confronting conflict directly	0.575	1.254	8.490	0.227
	31. working long hours (R)	-0.671			
	37. result oriented	0.467			
	40. being highly organized	0.576			
5	2. stability	0.591	1.201	8.381	0.627
	7. rule oriented	0.792			
	9. attention to detail	0.622			
6	18. being aggressive	0.758	1.113	8.148	0.660
	21. achievement oriented	0.499			
	35. having a good reputation	0.593			
	39. being competitive	0.719			
Total				56.73	0.889

The 6th item in the 3rd factor and the 31th in the 4th factor decreased the reliability of sub-scales. Therefore, these items are deleted from sub-scales. Internal reliability increased to 0.726 for 3rd dimension, to 0.657 for 4th dimension. The dimensions are named considering the content of items loaded and adhering original sub-scale names as much as possible. 1-respect for people 2-development and attention to rewards 3- innovativeness 4- result oriented 5- detail oriented and stability 6- competitiveness.

Big five personality dimensions: Turkish version of NEO-FF is adapted by Gulgoz and dimension scores for each participant are calculated by him. Turkish culture adapted version of the scale included sampling in this research is tested for validity and reliability by the researcher. Standardized t scores are utilized for this research.

Group performance: 6 items are loaded to one dimension as expected. Explained variance of this scale is 65.9 % and cronbach alpha is 0.89. (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin: 0.88; Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: 0.00)

4.2. The effects of fit dimensions on group performance

Structural equation modeling is utilized for test the relationships proposed. Standardized path coefficients for group performance model are shown at Figure 1. T values of relationships and goodness of fit index for the model are shown at Table 2 and 3, respectively.

Figure 1: Standardized path coefficients for group performance model

Table 2: t values of relationships

Relationships	t values
perceptual similarity → group performance	3,50
value congruence → group performance	-8,15
Personality traits congruence → group performance	3,69

Table 3 : goodness of fit index for the model

	X ² /d.f.	RMSEA	GFI	AGFI	SRMR	NNFI	CFI
acceptable	< 5	< 0,08	>0,90	>0,90	<0,08	>0,90	>0,90
calculated	3,43	0,06	0,90	0,88	0,059	0,92	0,93

Considering all fit index scores, it can be expressed that the fit of the model is at good level.

Depending on significant t values of relationships, group performance is influenced by perceptual similarity, value congruence, and personality traits congruence.

Group perf = 0.19*perceptual similarity – 0.41*difference between individual values and group values + 0.23 difference between individual personal values and group personal values

Value differentiation is the most efficient fit component on group performance, negatively as expected. Perceptual similarity and differentiation in personality traits affect group performance, positively. The relationship with perceptual similarity is relatively weak.

According to these findings, hypotheses H₁ and H₃ are accepted, H₂ is rejected.

5. Conclusion and suggestion

5.1. Conclusion

Value congruence, personality trait congruence, and individual's perception about demographic similarity with group and job execution similarity with coworkers/supervisor affect group performance. Job execution similarity

with supervisor as an antecedent of group performance has significant effect. Supervisor is perceived as efficient in project group. If the employees perceive their attitudes of job execution as highly similar to those of supervisor, they perceive group performance at high level. The employees are identified with their supervisors in terms of job execution attitude.

Personality traits differentiation from group in general meaning increased group performance. It can be expressed that the employees having different personality traits affect group functioning, positively. This finding is supportive for the research made by Glomb and Welsh (2005). The researchers pay attention to positive effects of differentiation in personality traits contrary to research proposing relationships between similarity in personality traits and desired outcomes. Some research findings show that heterogeneity of personality traits affect group performance positively more than homogeneity of traits (Aamodt ve Kimbrough, 1982; Ghiselli ve Lodahl, 1958; Moynihan ve Peterson, 2001).

Individual, environmental and time-related factors determine what dimension has the most remarkable effect on experiencing person-environment fit (Jansen and Kristof-Brown, 2006). Jansen and Kristof-Brown (2006) highlighted that when individuals evaluate person-environment fit for themselves, they give more importance to fit with prominent dimension(s) of environment (Shin, 2005). Kristof-Brown et. al (2002) stated that individual's previous working experience affect the importance attributed by individual for fit types (Jansen and Kristof-Brown, 2006).

Strategic position of organization and environment are important determiner for shared culture perceptions because they shape organization structure and control systems (Joyce and Slocum, 1990). Therefore, in addition to view proposed with attraction-selection-attrition theory that individuals' personality traits make organization (working group) culture, role of environmental characteristics for developing organization (group) culture can not be ignored.

5.2. Managerial implications and further study

Person-group fit and types of fit are considered for function of personnel selection/recruitment and retain employees in human resource management.

Traditional job analysis is not enough to select an employee for group-oriented work environments. Traditional job analysis is utilized for determining the level of knowledge, skill, and ability so as to execute job. This type of analysis is carried out at individual level, it ignores analysis at group level for group-oriented works in personnel selection process. Therefore, evaluating person-job fit, person-group fit, and person-organization fit synchronously is a robust approach in personnel selection process (Barber, 1998). In this way, the relative importance of perception about person-job fit, person-group fit, and person-organization fit can be evaluated in job choice (Carless, 2005).

The effect of value congruence in strong/weak cultures is considerable factor for human resource management. Acceptance or rejection of individual behavior is prominent in strong cultures. Individuals in the organization having strong cultures have similar perception about organization (group)' s operations and the tool/way of pursuing goals (DelCampo, 2006). There is agreement about values among employees. Diagnosing cultural values is more difficult for individuals in weak cultures, and they have opportunity to shape cultural values. For this viewpoint, turnover rate is lower. Consistent with these views, Ashfort (1987) stated that the organizations (groups) having strong culture enhance culture. The researcher investigated the moderators of power of culture on the relationship between person-organization fit and turnover. Strong cultures react for values harder than weak cultures. Therefore, management should consider power of culture in the organization in addition to value congruence.

Diagnosing moderators of the relationship fit-satisfaction/performance is questionable research field to minimize the effects of misfit and to utilize the different viewpoints stemming from heterogeneity of working values and personality traits (Erdogan, et. al, 2004). Kristof-Brown (2005) suggested that moderator variables such as dispositional/individual and environmental characteristics and mediation variables should be diagnosed.

Complementary fit is seldom attributed for emerging person-organization fit in the literature (Shin, 2005). It is not possible to ignore the interaction paradigm for explaining the effect of personality on behavior in organization literature. Even though the interaction paradigm is frequently attributed, there is no research comparing the explanatoriness of interaction depending on complementary fit and supplementary fit (Kausel and Slaughter, 2001). The proposed fit between person and group will be measured according to aspect of complementary fit. The effects of fit components on group performance should be examined.

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